

The Impact of Social Media Marketing on Traditional Media Strategies in Qatari Institutions

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Abstract

This paper examines how the growing use of social media platforms has influenced the effectiveness and role of traditional media marketing in Qatari institutions. It analyzes the positive and negative impacts of social media on advertising strategies, including cost, audience engagement, and the use of celebrity endorsement. Drawing on existing literature, the study highlights the shift in marketing dynamics and provides insights into how organizations in Qatar can integrate social and traditional media to achieve optimal outreach and communication efficiency.

Keywords

Social Media, Traditional Media, Marketing Strategy, Qatar, Digital Transformation, Celebrity Endorsement

Main Content

Social Media Marketing on Traditional Media Marketing Advertisements Organizations

Introduction:

Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube etc. continue to make significant impacts on the lives of people, especially, the young people (Chatzithomas et al., 2014; Farooq & Jan, 2012). The growth of the social network users has compelled organizations to make use of this modern domain to conduct their marketing of products and services (Farooq & Jan, 2012). Various social media platforms permit organizations to market their goods by using the different tools given by them. For instance, Facebook has provided various tools for marketing for organizations to reach their consumer through the use of groups, creating pages, and using social ads (Farooq & Jan, 2012).

Social networking sites characterize an important challenge in businesses, as many traditional marketing methods are being regarded as inadequate and not well-matched with the increasing number of consumers that are empowered (Chatzithomas et al., 2014). According to Chatzithomas et al. (2014), in this modern era that is characterised by globalization, organizations need to consider both social and traditional media marketing strategies to achieve their goals.

Even though the use of the internet has upgraded some elements of marketing, research has been carried out on the effects the internet has had on marketing (Cowden, 2014). These have indicated that marketing goals and the roles of marketing are still the same irrespective of the media used. The internet has not changed the goals of marketing but has only added another relevant tool to be used in the same (Cowden, 2014). It, however, gives an amalgam element in the marketing field through the blending of features of the traditional media advertising, of integrated marketing communications and the important channel of communication (Chatzithomaset al., 2014). With the integration of the social media in marketing, it has brought about some impacts on the earlier traditional media marketing tools, for instance, the use of TV, radios and newspapers. This research, therefore, intends to assess the impacts of social media marketing on traditional media marketing, with a focus on major institutions on Qatar.

With the increasing trend in the use of social media, businesses have also incorporated its use in the marketing of products and services (Neti, 2011). Social media has improved on the traditional marketing tools that were being used. However, on its own, social media marketing cannot single-handedly promote the development of an enterprise (Odhiambo, 2012). Since its incorporation in the marketing field, the use of social media and celebrities have had an effect on business developments and growth (Neti, 2011). Its use has brought about some impacts on the traditional media advertisement companies, as well as on marketing itself.

Limited research has been conducted on the impacts of social media marketing on the earlier traditional media marketing methods. The purpose of this study will, therefore, be to

assess these impacts and also aim to further expound on the impacts of social media on general marketing.

Aim and Objectives of the study

The aim of the study will be to investigate the impacts of social media marketing on traditional media marketing.

The objectives will be;

- To assess the positive impacts of social media marketing on marketing advertisement in major institutions in Qatar.
- To determine the negative impacts of social media marketing on traditional media institutions.
- To determine the benefits of using celebrities on marketing advertisements
- To evaluate the impacts of using social media in marketing management.

Research questions

- What are the positive impacts of using social media marketing on marketing advertisements in the major institutions in Qatar?
- What are the negative impacts of social media marketing on traditional media institutions?
- What are the benefits of using celebrities on marketing advertisements?
- What are the impacts of using social media in marketing management?

Literature review

In the recent past, the marketing field has experienced a gradual change and evolution with the development of digital technology. Marketing departments of major organizations are now using the internet and other digital media platforms rather than the earlier advertising media e.g., newspapers and radios (Cowden, 2014). With the creation and global use of social media, the marketing field has also been forced to make changes so as to incorporate the use of social media platforms like Facebook and twitter, so as to stay connected to their consumers.

A number of studies have been conducted on the use of social media in the marketing field, however, very few studies have been conducted on the influence it has had on the traditional marketing media (Paquette, 2013). In a literature review by Paquette (2013), it was reported that social media platforms have grown from giving people a link to keep in touch with friends and family to a platform where customers find out more on their preferred companies for their goods and services. On the other hand, it also reported that marketers

also use the social media platforms for a convenience in reaching their consumers. Nevertheless, more and more individuals continue to perceive the marketing services on social media as exciting and easy to access unlike traditional media marketing (Cha, 2009 cited in Paquette, 2013). However, there is limited research that has been done to examine the effects of using social media for marketing on advertisement companies.

The use of social media in marketing

In a literature review conducted by Adzharuddin (2012), it was discovered that social media marketing permits interactions and gives a two-way communication, showing consumers as lively rather than inactive parties, unlike traditional media marketing. The use of the social media platforms in marketing has provided organizations with cheap, convenient, easily measurable and immediate platform to reach the consumers (Adzharuddin, 2012). Current statistics have shown that the use of social media in marketing is growing stronger and its use is expected to grow exponentially (Cowden, 2014).

One of the reasons that have propelled organizations into the use of social media in marketing is the high costs that traditional marketing media require (Cowden, 2014). According to Kobliski (2006, cited in Cowden, 2014), research has shown that placing an advert in the newspaper may cost between \$200-\$20,000 USD, depending on the assignment and magnitude of the publication while TV adverts were reported to be even more expensive. These prices compared to making adverts on the internet are much higher and this is one of the reasons that steer people to use social media in marketing.

Cox (2010, cited in Paquette, 2013) examined the relationship between age and the likelihood of individuals to use social media for products and services. The results showed that the young people, especially, those falling between the ages of 18 and 28 had a positive attitude towards the use of online videos, blogs and other social media sites for searching for products. Those individuals between the ages of 35 and 54 showed a preference to the use of video and brand channels advertisement formats and found them to be attractive and informative. The study did not, however, spell out the impacts of the social media on the traditional marketing methods.

Odhiambo (2012), designed a study to evaluate if social media marketing is more effective than the use of traditional media, using a particular company as a case study. The results showed that social media marketing is indeed more effective, however, it cannot be used on its own without enhancing it through the other traditional media publicity methods. These results indicated that social media cannot be used singly to promote or even develop a business. The limitation of this study was that the sample used as related to one company and therefore was too small to be used to make the correct inferences for other organizations.

The role of social media celebrities on marketing

It is no doubt that social media has become of significance in the lives of the young people. The young generation is practically living their lives on the internet and this can be seen in

how they dress, eat, behave and shopping is not excluded. Pate & Adams (2013) conducted a research to assess the influence of social media on the purchasing behaviours, particularly on the influence of celebrities, family and friends on purchases. The research was a survey conducted in two Universities. The results of the study revealed that the participants had strong regards to social media and the opinions given by their friends in these sites were also highly regarded. The respondents also revealed that they are more likely to buy products that have been 'liked' by their friends on these social media sites. The study also revealed that there was an association between age and the liking of commodities endorsed by celebrities. The limitation of this study was that it only involved students and no other people in the real world to determine their preferences.

Mwendwa (2014), conducted a review to examine the impact of celebrity endorsement in marketing on consumer habits, using secondary sources in the past 20 years. The results indicated that celebrity endorsement has an impact on purchase habits and that there are factors that contribute to celebrities influence on their audience. These were found to include; identity, where people follow actions of celebrities in order to identify with them, and the use of the media itself has also had an effect on the young people following their favourite stars.

Effects of social media marketing on traditional marketing

Cowden (2014), in her literature, stated that in order to comprehend the impacts of social media marketing on traditional marketing, that it is of significance to comprehend how the traditional marketing method are perceived currently. Barlow and Birkhahn (2005 cited in Cowden, 2014) conducted surveys to examine the perception of marketing officers, consumers, and advertising officials on mass marketing. Executives like the top marketing official of McDonalds responded that mass marketing is not effective in the contemporary business world, while consumers (63%), still believed that traditional marketing methods like TVs and magazines are still effective in the marketing of products and services. The results also showed that two factors are responsible for the declined apparent effectiveness of traditional marketing. These include; the noisy, disorderly modern mass media and alternative media such as social media being more attractive to consumers (Barlow & Birkhahn, 2005 cited in Cowden, 2014). The limitation of this study, however, is that it did not incorporate the age differences in the study which would have given a more defined preference with respect to age.

Social Media and Marketing Management

The integration of the internet in marketing has brought about a different route or approach to the marketing field. Through the use of the social media, there have been some slight upgrades or improvements in marketing and in turn it has brought about changes in the management of marketing. Abuhashesh (2014) conducted a research to analyse the effects of integrating the internet into advertising, marketing, public relations and the management of customer service. Data was collected from secondary sources which included the previous studies and research that have been conducted on the integration of the internet in

marketing. The results of the study indicated that the use of the internet in advertising and marketing has improved customer services and also improved on public relations as well as easing the management of marketing. The results also indicated that these benefits are more on the small companies as they save funds which would otherwise be used on TV or other outdoor advertising that are quite costly. The limitation of the study was on the methodology used which relied on secondary sources from previous studies which are unreliable since technology and internet use has improved and the results, therefore, cannot be used to make accurate inferences.

Research plan

This study will employ the use of both qualitative and quantitative research designs (mixed method). Qualitative research will be necessary for the discovery and comprehension of the participants' experiences and viewpoints (Harwell, 2011). Qualitative research gives a natural interpretative approach to phenomena in order to give valid conclusions and meaning (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005, cited in Harwell, 2011). This type of research method can be described as inductive as it allows the researcher to create hypothesis and conceptualizations from the data given by the respondent (Harwell, 2011; Creswell, 2003). This research method will allow the researcher to observe for real situations as well as being the suitable method to give answers to some of the research questions. The advantage of using this method is that the researchers cannot ignore their familiarities, skills, and biases and therefore did not to be strict objective bystanders to the current research (Harwell, 2011)

Qualitative research also allows the researcher to make conclusions based principally on participants' experiences and therefore gives descriptions of events and issues as they have been previously perceived (Creswell, 2003). This will aid in discovering the impacts the use of social media marketing on the marketing advertising in the major institutions in Qatar. It will also shed light on the impacts the use of social media has had on the other traditional marketing methods and media. Qualitative research is also important in testing a theory or hypothesis as well as in trying to explain a phenomenon that requires understanding because sufficient research has not been conducted to explain it (Creswell, 2003). For instance, in this study, the research method will try to determine the impacts of social media marketing on traditional media marketing since not much have been explored on this phenomena. The use of qualitative research will also explore widely the importance of celebrities in marketing, as it is useful in at points which the researcher does not completely comprehend which study variables to explore (Creswell, 2003).

Quantitative research will help to examine the extent of the impacts of the use of social media marketing on the traditional marketing media in Qatar. Quantitative research uses posts positivist privileges for developing information, for instance, the use of numeric and observations (Delice, 2010), and it utilizes surveys, and assemblage of data on predetermined instruments to yield statistical data for analysis. Quantitative research also tries to exploit objectivity, duplicability, and oversimplification of outcomes and are

naturally concerned about prediction (Harwell, 2011). For instance in the current study, the approach will allow for the prediction of the future of traditional marketing methods.

Population and sample

The population of interest of this study includes the marketing officials in various institutions in Qatar. For the qualitative design, the study sample will include two public relations officials from five institutions (n=10) including Qatar airways, Ooredoo company, QNB Bank Qatar post office branch, Qatar communication company and Al Mana Media advertising company. Emails will be sent to the potential participants requesting an audience so as to schedule interviews. For the qualitative design, this sample size will be sufficient since if the sample size is too large, it may lead to repetitiveness (Mason, 2010). Also, this gives the researcher the time to exhaust the questions and collect rich information (Mason, 2010). For the quantitative design, the sample size will include employees and consumers from the same organizations. The employees to be included in the study will be those from the marketing departments in the different organizations (n=20), that will be 4 from each department. On the other hand, four consumers from the different organizations will be selected to take part in the study (n=20). That will give a total of 50 respondents which will be a good number for the study. The study will utilize convenience sampling since this involves using samples that are available, easy to reach and willing to take part in the study (Teddlie & Yu, 2007).

Research Instruments

The research instrument for the qualitative approach will be in-depth unstructured interviews. This is because it will provide lengthy and focused discussions between the responsible parties to learn what is of significance to the researcher and how the participants comprehend the key elements with regards to their own experiences (Harwell, 2011). Also, using interviews in data collection might raise other relevant points that may not have been anticipated initially, which improves the quality of information that is collected (Harwell, 2011). The interviews will be recorded using a digital voice recorder with the permission of the respondent, for the purposes of clarity during the analysis.

Closed-ended questionnaires will be used to collect data for the quantitative design as the research instrument. The questions in the questionnaires will give the respondents answer choices to help them in answering the questions. A five-point Likert scale ranging from 1)strongly agree to 5) strongly disagree, will be used to assess the level of agreement for various statements such as; 1) Social media has improved the process of marketing in this organization, 2) Social media poses challenges to the traditional marketing media,etc. Using these structured questionnaires will be advantageous because they are quicker for the respondents to answer, allows for comparison of answers from different respondents and the answers from the respondents will be easy to code and analyse statistically (Delice, 2010).

Data analysis

Data from the interviews will be analysed using the inductive approach since not much is known about the phenomenon (Burnard et al., 2008), of the impacts of the use of social media marketing on the traditional media marketing. The interviews will be transcribed verbatim where the researcher will listen to the already recorded interviews to note the theories in the margin of words. This will give a summary of the discussed elements in the interview (Burnard et al., 2008). The researcher will then use the NVivo software version 11 to categorize and organize similar concepts and finally make conclusions. Data from the questionnaires will also be coded and analysed using SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics, for instance, percentages, frequencies, standard deviation and means will be used to give the explanatory scrutiny of the study variables.

Limitation of the study

The current study has threats to the validity of the results which include; the small sample size that will be used in the study. Fifty respondents for the sample size is small and therefore not a good representation of the population of Qatar. Another limitation is that the study only uses five companies in Qatar which may not be relevant in generalization since the other companies may have different ideas on the subject. Also, the current study is cross-sectional and may therefore not capture the future impacts of marketing using the internet on the traditional methods.

Ethical considerations

Obtaining a signed informed consent from the participants is a major ethical issue in carrying out a research (Fouka & Mantzorou, 2011). This consent will show that an individual voluntarily and intelligently gave his consent to take part in the study and also shows respect to the participants. Additionally, the consent shows the role of the respondent in the study and illustrates the clear purpose of the study. The current study will also require an approval from an ethical review board to guarantee that all ethical concerns in a research are followed to the latter.

Expected Outcomes

The current study aims to examine and assess the impacts of using social media marketing on traditional media marketing. The questions the study will focus on answering are; 1) whether the use of social media has an effect on advertisement companies, 2) whether social media marketing affects traditional media marketing, 3) whether using celebrities in advertisements improves on marketing and the general effects of using social media advertisements on marketing. The study is expected to give negative impacts on the traditional media marketing as well as have positive impacts in the marketing field. However, further studies should be conducted on these impacts while focusing on curbing the limitations earlier mentioned in the study.

Time table to complete thesis

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